

IMPACT OF DIGITAL MARKETING ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study evaluated the impact of digital marketing on Nigeria's socio-economic development and sustainability. The study was conducted to determine if social media impacts on job creation in Nigeria and to examine the effect of email marketing on environmental preservation in Nigeria. A simple random selection of 181 sample size of a population of 331 was used. The respondents completed a Likert scale-structured questionnaire. To display the frequency and percentage of responses from the respondents, the data was evaluated and displayed in descriptive tables. With the help of SPSS Version 26, a linear regression statistical technique was utilized to evaluate the hypotheses. The results show that social media strongly influences the generation of jobs in Nigeria, and that; email marketing has significant effect on environmental preservation in Nigeria. The study concludes that digital marketing propels economic expansion, generates job opportunities, improves information accessibility, and fosters environmental awareness; and recommends that, businesses and policymakers should recognize its potential and leverage its benefits to foster sustainable socio-economic development.

Keywords: Digital marketing, Socio-economic, Development, Sustainability

1 INTRODUCTION

Digital marketing is a powerful force in today's globalized and technology-driven world, revolutionizing the way businesses connect with consumers and impacting socio-economic development and sustainability. Digital marketing encompasses a wide range of online strategies and platforms, consisting of content production, advertising via email, social media, and search engine optimization (SEO). Its profound impact on socio-economic development and sustainability is evident across various sectors and regions. One significant area where digital marketing contributes to socio-economic development is through stimulating economic growth. As businesses leverage digital marketing techniques, they gain access to a global marketplace, enabling them to reach a broader audience and expand their customer base. This expansion leads to increased sales, revenue, and profitability, ultimately driving economic growth (Kapoor & Kansal, 2020). Furthermore, digital marketing provides chances for small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) to take on bigger companies on an even playing field, fostering entrepreneurship and diversifying the business landscape. Additionally, digital marketing plays a vital role in job creation and employment opportunities. The rise of digital marketing agencies and the need for knowledgeable digital marketers has given rise to a

new industry. Organizations require professionals adept in data analysis, SEO, content development, and social media management to drive their digital marketing campaigns effectively. This demand for specialized skills has created employment opportunities, particularly for the younger generation (Khan, 2019). By nurturing a skilled workforce, digital marketing contributes to human capital development and overall socio-economic progress.

Furthermore, digital marketing enhances access to information and knowledge sharing, leading to socio-economic development. With the proliferation of internet connectivity and the rise of social media platforms, individuals have access to a vast amount of information at their fingertips. Businesses leverage digital marketing to disseminate information about their products, services, and industry trends, empowering consumers to make informed decisions. Moreover, digital platforms facilitate knowledge exchange, collaboration, and networking, enabling individuals and communities to share ideas, expertise, and resources for mutual benefit (Marimuthu & Rajini, 2019). This democratization of information contributes to socio-economic development by empowering individuals and fostering collective intelligence.

Finally, digital marketing has the potential to drive sustainability by reducing environmental impact. Traditional marketing methods often involve the production and distribution of physical materials, leading to resource depletion and waste generation. In contrast, digital marketing minimizes the need for printed materials and physical advertising, resulting in reduced paper consumption, carbon emissions, and waste generation (Kaur, 2019). By adopting digital marketing practices, organizations can contribute to environmental sustainability and align their operations with green initiatives.

The impact of digital marketing on socio-economic development and sustainability in Nigeria has garnered significant attention. However, specific areas of focus within this broad topic require further exploration. This study aims to address two key objectives: first, to determine the social media's effect on job creation; second, to ascertain if email marketing has consequences on environmental preservation. Understanding how social media platforms influence employment opportunities is crucial for assessing the socio-economic impact of digital marketing. By investigating this objective, we can gain insights into the role of social media in stimulating entrepreneurship, fostering skill development, and creating job prospects for the Nigerian population. Email marketing has emerged as an effective and efficient tool for businesses to communicate with customers, disseminate information, and drive sales. However, the environmental implications of email marketing in Nigeria require careful examination. Investigating the effect of email marketing on environmental preservation in Nigeria will shed light on its potential to reduce paper consumption, waste generation, and carbon emissions, thus contributing to sustainable development.

By addressing these objectives, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of digital marketing on socio-economic development and sustainability in Nigeria.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1.1 Digital Marketing

Digital marketing, according to Anjum, More, and Ghouri (2012), is the use of the internet to aid in the sale of products and services. It entails the application of varieties of technology, such as digital media and software, to marketing exploration and interaction. To elicit a reaction from potential buyers, digital marketing employs all aspects of online advertising. E-marketing, according to Menberu (2017), is "employing digital media and the Internet to help sell goods and services." Regardless of the size or kind of organization, online technology has completely changed the field of marketing through the enhancement of conventional marketing activities. Marketing used to be done via telegraph, however, since the advent of electronic media, including radio, television, email, and the telephone, that notion has changed. Online marketing, as described by Rajarajan (2016), is a "collection of effective instruments and techniques utilized for advertising goods and services online." Due to the number of online marketing venues, digital marketing

employs a wider range of marketing techniques than conventional marketing. E-marketing is the term used by Nizam (2015) to describe the online promotion of products and services. More and more consumers are using the internet to make purchases of goods and services. Digital marketing is sometimes referred to as internet marketing (i-marketing), online marketing, or web marketing. Similar to traditional marketing, e-marketing involves creating a plan that enables businesses to reach the appropriate audiences with the appropriate messages and products/services, according to Menberu (2017). From the aforementioned definitions of the term "e-marketing," it is clear that there is agreement on electronic marketing as the procedure for marketing goods and services through the use of all electronic technology.

2.1.2 Social Media

The term "social media" describes online forums and tools that allow users to collaborate, share material, and engage in interactive communication (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). These platforms provide individuals, communities, and organizations with the ability to create, publish, and share user-generated content in various formats, encompassing written words, pictures, sounds, and videos. People can utilize social media platforms to connect, engage, and interact with others through features such as profiles, news feeds, comments, likes, shares, and direct messaging. Social media platforms have become integral to online communication and have significantly transformed the way individuals and businesses engage with each other and with wider audiences. They offer opportunities for information dissemination, social networking, online communities, and content discovery. Prominent social media sites include YouTube, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, and TikTok.

In the context of business and marketing, social media forums offer valuable opportunities for organizations to promote their brands, products, or services. Businesses can create official accounts or pages, engage with their target audience, and run programs of focused advertisement to attract new clients. Social media forums provide powerful tools for businesses to listen to customer feedback, address inquiries, and build brand loyalty.

2.1.3 Job Creation

Job creation refers to the process by which new employment opportunities are generated within an economy or a specific industry, leading to the expansion of the workforce and reduction in unemployment rates (Bassanini & S carpetta, 2002). It involves the establishment of new businesses, the growth of existing enterprises, or the introduction of new positions within organizations, resulting in the addition of jobs that provide income and employment for individuals. The potential for social media to create jobs is a key component of its economics. On social media, there are countless job options. Publication, trade, marketing, education, counseling, and a wide range of services are a few examples (Barnes, Hood, and Gallardo, 2013). The fact that these internet services are available suggests that social media creates jobs. Through the use of social media technology, productivity and income distribution are improved in society by providing people with these employment alternatives.

2.1.4 Environmental Preservation

Environmental preservation refers to the conscious and deliberate efforts aimed at safeguarding and conserving natural resources, ecosystems, and biodiversity to maintain ecological balance and ensure long-term sustainability (Borrini-Feyerabend et al., 2004). It involves the protection, restoration, and sustainable management of natural environments, including forests, wetlands, oceans, wildlife habitats, and other ecosystems. The concept of environmental preservation is rooted in the recognition of the intrinsic value of nature and the understanding that human activities can have significant impacts on the environment. It encompasses various principles and practices aimed at minimizing environmental degradation, preventing the loss of biodiversity, mitigating pollution, and promoting sustainable use of natural resources. One key aspect of environmental preservation is the conservation of biodiversity. Biodiversity refers to the variety of species, ecosystems, and genetic resources found on Earth. Environmental preservation recognizes the importance of preserving biodiversity as it helps maintain the resilience and stability of ecosystems and

provides vital ecological services. (CBD,1992). Protecting and conserving biodiversity entails creating protected areas, putting programs in place to save species, and encouraging sustainable resource and land management techniques (Balmford et al., 2005).

2.1.5 Digital Marketing Strategies and Success Factors

In contemporary times, organizations undergo digital transformation that prompts them to reassess their structure, tools, and strategy (Taherdoost, Sahibuddin & Jalaliyoon, 2013). A marketing strategy serves as the logic through which a business unit aims to achieve its marketing objectives (Olannye, 2017). It is a plan devised to generate ongoing value for the organization. It is widely acknowledged that a well-developed digital strategy is crucial for companies in order to guide their actions and maximize their business goals in the next normal. Without a digital strategy, companies may invest in expensive technologies without effectively attaining their business objectives (Chaffey, 2015). Undoubtedly, organizations in developed economies have reported significant savings through digital marketing, enabling efficient communication, quick response, and effective information sharing with customers/clients (Laudon & Traver, 2017). Therefore, as the next normal brings about rapid and radical shifts in strategies, structures, systems, processes, and technology (Bello, 2020), Integrated internet strategies that include digital adoption solutions are urgently needed to support marketing firms in developing countries with risk mitigation, revenue growth, and cost reduction (Sneader& Singhal, 2020).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Diffusion of Innovation theory (Rogers, 2003).

Everett Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation theory examines how new concepts, innovations, or technology are embraced and dispersed within a community or social structure (Rogers, 2003). This theory offers a framework for comprehending the reasons and means by which innovations are accepted by individuals, organizations, or communities, and how they ultimately contribute to socio-economic development and sustainability. The Diffusion of Innovation theory can be used in the context of digital marketing to analyze the adoption and impact of digital marketing strategies and technologies in Nigeria. According to this hypothesis, adopters can be divided into five groups based on their readiness to accept new innovations: innovators, early adopters, late adopters, and losers. Gaining knowledge about the traits and actions of different adopter groups can help one understand how digital marketing strategies are spreading throughout Nigeria. The theory also highlights several factors that influence the adoption and diffusion of innovations, such as perceived relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, and the ability to try the innovation on a small scale. Applying these factors to the context of digital marketing in Nigeria helps assess the extent of adoption and integration of digital marketing practices into socio-economic activities.

Researchers can utilize this theory to examine digital marketing vis-à-vis socio-economic development and sustainability in Nigeria. This analysis involves studying adoption patterns, identifying barriers and facilitators, understanding the characteristics of early adopters, evaluating the influence of adoption factors, and assessing the impact of digital marketing on indicators like employment, business growth, income generation, and environmental sustainability.

2.3 Empirical Reviews

The influence of social media on employment generation and economic expansion in Taiwan was investigated by Tsai and Wu (2015). This study looks at how social media affects Taiwan's economic expansion and employment development. The researchers collected data from various sources, including government reports and social media platforms, and conducted statistical analyses to ascertain social media's connection with job creation. The findings indicate that social media usage positively influences job creation and contributes to economic growth in Taiwan. The study suggests that social media can be an effective tool for promoting entrepreneurship, connecting job seekers with employers, and facilitating business expansion.

Mellahi, Frynas & Finlay (2014) on Global Strategic Management. This comprehensive study explores the global strategic management practices of multinational corporations (MNCs) and their use of social media for job creation. The researchers conducted interviews and surveys with executives from various MNCs to investigate how social media platforms are utilized to attract talent, enhance employer branding, and facilitate recruitment processes. The study highlights the increasing importance of social media in MNCs' talent acquisition strategies and its positive impact on job creation globally.

Mont, (2004) on institutionalization of sustainable consumption patterns based on shared use. This study explores the concept of sustainable consumption and highlights the importance of sharing and collaborative consumption as a means to reduce environmental impacts. Although not directly related to email marketing, the study suggests that practices such as sharing resources and information digitally can contribute to environmental preservation by reducing the need for physical goods and minimizing resource consumption. Nordman and Doumer (2009) employed a first-hand survey with a representative data sample of 2000 people to examine the role of social network transitions in West African labor markets. They discovered that social networks do, in fact, have a significant impact on labor market outcomes using extremely detailed information about social networks and discrete-time data; however, this influence varies depending on the social network's considered dimension rather than its overall size.

3 METHODOLOGY

In order to explore impact of digital marketing on socio-economic development and sustainability in Nigeria, a survey design was used. A simple random selection of 181 sample size from a population of 331 from staff of first bank and access bank within Enugu metropolis was used. A questionnaire structured in a Likert scale with values of (SA=5; A=4; UD=3; SD=4; D=5) was given to respondents in order to collect data from the chosen firms for this study. The data was analyzed and presented in descriptive tables to show the frequency and percentage of responses from the respondents. Linear regression statistical tool was used to test the hypotheses with the aid of SPSS Version 26.

4 ANALYSIS

4.1 Data Presentation

Table 4.1: Social Media have effect on job creation in Nigeria

Options	SA Freq(%)	A Freq(%)	U Freq(%)	D Freq(%)	SD Freq(%)	Mean	Std
I often find job opportunities and have been contacted by potential employers through social media platforms	126(73.3)	30(17.4)	13(7.6)	3(1.7)	0(0.0)	1.38	0.70
Social media platforms play a significant role in job creation and employment opportunities in Nigeria	132(76.7)	22(12.8)	9(5.2)	9(5.2)	0(0.0)	1.39	0.81
There have been increase in job opportunities and shift in employment trends in Nigeria due to the influence of social media platforms	130(75.6)	34(19.8)	5(2.9)	2(1.2)	1(0.6)	1.31	0.64

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.1 shows the response of the respondents on the effect of social media on job creation in Nigeria. It shows that 126(73.3%) strongly agree that they often find job opportunities and have been contacted by potential employers through social media platforms, 30(17.4%) of them agree, while 13(7.6%) of them were undecided to this assertion, 3(1.7%) of them disagree. With the mean and standard deviation of 1.38 ± 0.70 , it implies that majority of the respondents strongly agree that they often find job opportunities and have been contacted by potential employers through social media platforms. The table further show that 132(76.7%) of them strongly agree that social media platforms play a significant role in job creation and employment opportunities in Nigeria, 22(12.8%) of them agree, whereas 9(5.2%) of them were undecided, and 9(5.2%) of them disagree. With the mean and standard deviation of 1.39 ± 0.81 , it implies that majority of the respondents strongly agree that social media platforms play a significant role in job creation and employment opportunities in Nigeria. It also shows that 130(75.6%) of them strongly agree that there have been increase in job opportunities and shift in employment trends in Nigeria due to the influence of social media platforms, 34(19.8%) of them agree, while 5(2.9%) of them were undecided to the assertion, 2(1.2%) of them disagree and 1(0.6%) of them strongly disagree. With a mean and standard deviation of 1.31 ± 0.64 , it implies that majority of the respondents strongly agree that there have been increase in job opportunities and shift in employment trends in Nigeria due to the influence of social media platforms.

4.2 Hypothesis One

H₁: Social media have significant effect on job creation in Nigeria

H₀: Social media does not have significant effect on job creation in Nigeria

Table 4.1.1 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.809 ^a	.655	.653	.48124	.526

Source: SPSS Version 26

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social media

b. Dependent Variable: Job creation

Table 4.1.2 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	74.816	1	74.816	323.058	.000 ^b
	Residual	39.370	170	.232		
	Total	114.186	171			

Source: SPSS Version 26

a. Dependent Variable: Job creation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Social media

Table 4.1.3 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.024	.084		.284	.777
	Social media	1.026	.057	.809	17.974	.000

Source: SPSS Version 26

a. Dependent Variable: Job creation

Result Summary

$R = .809$, $R^2 = .655$, $F = 323.058$, $T = 17.974$, $DW = .526$

Interpretation of the Result

To seek how social media relates to creation of jobs in Nigeria, a linear regression was carried out. Tables 4.1.1 – 4.1.3 shows that there is strong positive relationship social media and job creation (R - coefficient = .809). Social media may explain 65.5% of the variation in job creation, according to the R square, with no autocorrelation because Durbin-Watson's (.526) value is less than 2. The estimate error for the linear regression model is small, at approximately .48124. The variance can be attributed to chance since the regression total of the squares (74.816) is greater than the residual sum of the squares (39.370). The model is significant, as indicated by the F -statistics = 323.058. The degree to which social media impact job creation with .809 value indicates a positive significance relationship between social media and job creation which is statistically significant (with $t = 17.974$) and $p = .000 < 0.05$.

Decision Rule

Reject null hypothesis (H_0) if P -Value < 0.05 and do not reject H_0 if otherwise

Decision

Since the P -Value $.000 < 0.05$, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and then conclude that social media have significant effect on job creation in Nigeria.

Table 4.2: Email marketing has effect on environmental preservation in Nigeria

Options	SA Freq(%)	A Freq(%)	U Freq(%)	D Freq(%)	SD Freq(%)	Mean	Std
I often receive promotional emails from businesses and organizations	136(79.1)	17(9.9)	7(4.1)	9(5.2)	3(1.7)	1.37	0.82
Email marketing highly contribute to raising awareness about environmental preservation in Nigeria	126(73.3)	32(18.6)	6(3.5)	3(1.7)	5(2.9)	1.38	0.74
I usually take environmentally friendly actions and make	115(66.9)	39(22.7)	7(4.1)	9(5.2)	2(1.2)	1.50	0.85

conscious decisions as a result of receiving emails promoting sustainable practices							
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Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.2 discusses the respondents' responses on how email marketing affects environmental preservation in Nigeria. It shows that 136(79.1%) of the respondents strongly agree that they often receive promotional emails from businesses and organizations, 17(9.9%) of them agree, whereas 7(4.1%) of them were undecided, 9(5.2%) of them disagree and 3(1.7%) of them strongly disagree.

Having mean and standard deviation of 1.37 ± 0.82 , it implies that majority of them strongly that they often receive promotional emails from businesses and organizations. It further shows that 126(73.3%) of them strongly agree that email marketing highly contribute to raising awareness about environmental preservation in Nigeria, 32(18.6%) of them agree, while 6(3.5%) of them were undecided, 3(1.7%) disagree and 5(2.9%) strongly disagree. With 1.38 ± 0.74 as the mean and standard deviation, it implies that email marketing highly contribute to raising awareness about environmental preservation in Nigeria. The table finally show that 115(66.9%) of the respondents strongly agree that they usually take environmentally friendly actions and make conscious decisions as a result of receiving emails promoting sustainable practices, 39(22.7%) of them agree, whereas 7(4.1%) of them were undecided to the assertion, 9(5.2%) of them disagree and 2(1.2%) strongly disagree. Mean and standard deviation value of 1.50 ± 0.85 , implies that majority of the respondents strongly agree that they usually take environmentally friendly actions and make conscious decisions as a result of receiving emails promoting sustainable practices.

4.3 Hypothesis Two

H₁: Email marketing has significant effect on environmental preservation in Nigeria

H₀: Email marketing does not have significant effect on environmental preservation in Nigeria

Table 4.2.1 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.858 ^a	.735	.734	.45147	.578

Source: SPSS Version 26

a. Predictors: (Constant), Email marketing

b. Dependent Variable: Environmental preservation

Table 4.2.2 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	96.343	1	96.343	472.671	.000 ^b
	Residual	34.651	170	.204		
	Total	130.994	171			

Source: SPSS Version 26

a. Dependent Variable: Environmental preservation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Email marketing

Table 4.2.3 Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	.137	.072		1.903	.059
	Email marketing	1.002	.046	.858	21.741	.000

Source: SPSS Version 26

a. Dependent Variable: Environmental preservation

Result Summary

$R = .858$, $R^2 = .735$, $F = 472.671$, $T = 21.741$, $DW = .578$

Interpretation of the Result

A linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the effect of email marketing on environmental preservation in Nigeria. (Tables 4.2.1 – 4.2.3) shows that there is strong positive relationship between email marketing and environmental preservation (R- coefficient = .858). The R square, the coefficient of determination, shows that 73.5% of the variation in environmental preservation can be explained by email marketing with no autocorrelation as Durbin-Watson (.578) is less than 2. With the linear regression model, the error of estimate is low, with a value of about .45147. The regression sum of the square 96.343 is more than the residual sum of the square 34.651 indicating that the variation is due to chance. The F-statistics = 472.671 shows that the model is significant. The extent to which email marketing impact environmental preservation with .858 value indicates a positive significance relationship between email marketing and environmental preservation which is statistically significant (with $t = 21.741$) and $p = .000 < 0.05$.

Decision Rule

Reject null hypothesis (Ho) if P-Value < 0.05 and do not reject Ho if otherwise

Decision

Since the P-Value $000 < 0.05$, we reject the null hypothesis (Ho) and then conclude that email marketing has significant effect on environmental preservation in Nigeria

5 DISCUSSION

The first objective was to determine the effect of social media on job creation in Nigeria. To achieve this objective, regression analysis was carried out between social media and job creation. The result reviewed that social media have significant effect on job creation in Nigeria. ($r = .809$; f-statistics = 323.058; $t = 17.974$; $p = .000 < 0.05$). This result can be likened to that of Tsai, & Wu, (2015), that studied the impact of social media on job creation and economic growth in Taiwan. And found that social media usage positively influences job creation and contributes to economic growth in Taiwan. The second objective was to examine the effect of email marketing on environmental preservation in Nigeria. To achieve this, regression analysis was carried out between email marketing and environmental preservation. The result show that email marketing have significant effect on environmental preservation in Nigeria ($r = .858$; f-statistics = 472.671; $t = 21.741$; $p = .000 < 0.05$). This result is similar to the finding by Mont, (2004) who carried out a study on Institutionalization of sustainable consumption patterns based on shared use. This

study explores the concept of sustainable consumption and highlights the importance of sharing and collaborative consumption as a means to reduce environmental impacts. The study indicated that practices such as sharing resources and information digitally can contribute to environmental preservation by reducing the need for physical goods and minimizing resource consumption.

6 CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

In conclusion, the impact of digital marketing on socio-economic development and sustainability is far-reaching. It drives economic growth, creates employment opportunities, enhances information access, and promotes environmental consciousness. As digital marketing continues to evolve, businesses and policymakers must recognize its potential and leverage its benefits to foster sustainable socio-economic development. Also, efforts must be made to explore other areas of digital marketing that may impact positively on the environment.

7 LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

This focal point of this study is on the impact of social media and email marketing on socio-economic development and sustainability in Nigeria. Other researchers can venture into other areas of digital marketing such as, content Marketing, affiliate marketing, mobile marketing, and search engine marketing among others.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Applicable.

Authors' Data Availability Statement: The qualitative data utilized for this study will be made available upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Declarations: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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